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PREVALENCE OF MENTAL RETARDATION IN CHILDREN WITH ADHD, AN EPIDEMIOLOGICAL STUDY, AT SIR C.J.INSTITUTE OF PSYCHIATRY, HYDERABAD

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ABSTRACT

Objectives: To determine the frequency of Mental retardation in children of attention deficit hyperactivity disorder. **Study Design:** A Cross-Sectional Study. **Patient and Method:** Study was conducted in the outpatient department (Clinics) of Sir Cowasjee Jahangir Institute of psychiatry Hyderabad. The study is of 06 months duration (1st January 2014 to 31st June 2014). Two hundred and fourteen (214) cases of ADHD age from 6years to 12 years were selected in this study. Non-probability consecutive sampling was done. Among patients with ADHD 6 months duration of symptoms either gender from age 6-12 years, attending Psychiatry clinic (OPD) at CJIP and LUH OPD were included in the study. Cases with Adverse General Medical Conditions, History of head injury, Head Injury, who deny/withdraw consent, were excluded. Data was collected on semi-structured Performa and analyzed through SPSS version 18 (PSW). **Results:** Out of 214 ADHD Children, mean age of the children was 9.50 years \pm SD 2.32, in which 160 (74.8%) were males and 54 (25.2%) were females. n=105 (49.1%) of cases were from rural area and n=109 (50.9%) were from urban area. Co-morbid Mental retardation was present in 53.3% cases, from which 69.2% were male and 30.7% were female (p-value 0.034). 48.1% of children attended schooling despite 51.9% had not attended schooling (p-value 0.005). **Conclusion:** ADHD commonly present in male children. Co-morbid Mental retardation is significantly present in children with ADHD. Despite urban ruler difference Male gender significant associated with co-morbid Mental retardation.

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INTRODUCTION

Childhood psychiatric disorder estimated 12% prevalence around the globe [1]. Two important childhood psychiatric disabilities are Attention deficit hyperactive disorder (ADHD) and Mental retardation [2,3], had significant prevalence, ADHD estimated from 5% to 15% prevalence and for MR 10% to 17% estimated [4,5]. ADHD is most thoroughly research disorders in medicine [6] associated with a broad range of negative outcome [7,8] and huge financial burden to families [9] which makes it a major public health problem [10]. Worldwide prevalence of ADHD is 5.29% in extensive review of literature [11].

Estimation of mental retardation in a study from Karachi Pakistan prevalence were 19.0/1000 children (95% confidence interval (CI) 13.5-24.4) for severe mental retardation and 65.3/1000 children (95% CI 48.9-81.8) for mild mental retardation, prevalence were considerably higher from industrialized countries and less develop countries [12]. A study from Lahore Pakistan publish in *acta paediatrica* showed prevalence of MR among 6 to 10 years old children was 6.2 per 100, and highest in slum (10.5) and lowest (1.3 per 100) in upper middle class group, factors were common like poverty, malnutrition, birth trauma [13].

Children with ADHD were more likely to have other mental health and neuro-developmental conditions, most children with ADHD had at least 1 co-morbid disorder, 33% had 1, 16% had 2, and 18% had 3 or more, the risk for having 3 or more co-morbidities was 3.8 times higher for poor versus affluent children (30% VS 8%) [14]. Presence of the co-morbid illness is a significant clinical subject as it complicates the diagnosis, treatment and prognosis [15]. Co-morbid disorders have a poorer outcome associated with significantly greater social, emotional, and psychological difficulties [16].

This is common impression that this is largely an American Disorder because predominance of American research in this field [17]. ADHD and mental retardation affects social, functional and academic performance. This study aims to determine frequency of Mental Retardation in children with ADHD in developing country.

METHODOLOGY

A descriptive cross-sectional study was conducted at the Psychiatric outpatient ambulatory care facilities of Sir Cowasjee Jahangir Institute of Psychiatry (CJIP) Hyderabad for a period of six months (1st January 2014 to 31st June 2014). We calculated a minimum sample size of 214. Cases were selected by non-probability consecutive sampling approach from the settings. The eligible cases were patients of ADHD (with all subtypes) clinically diagnosed on the basis of DSM-4, of either gender with an age range of 6-12 years, attended psychiatry outpatient clinics at CJIP and LUH during study time period and given verbal consent. Cases with general medical conditions, head injury, and who refuse to participate were excluded from the study. The data was recorded on a semi-structured questionnaire from the study participants/parents after informed consent. The diagnostic tools used to access the outcome were Vanderbilt ADHD Diagnostic Parent Rating Scale^{II} and DSM-IV-TR (Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders)³. Intellectual disability was clinically diagnosed on the basis of DSM-4 and categorized either YES or NO. Data was analyzed by using SPSS software (version-18). The frequency and percentages of categorical variables was calculated while for numerical variables the mean \pm SD was used, Chi-square test applied $P \leq 0.05$ to ensure for associations.

RESULTS

214 children of ADHD were recruited mean age of the patients was 9.50 years \pm SD 2.32 with age range from 7-12 years (Table No 1). More of the participants were male 160 (74.8%) and 54 (25.2%) female (p-value 0.034). N=103 (48.1%) of the children attended schooling and 111 (51.9%) didn't attend (p-value 0.005). Co-morbid mental retardation was significantly observed in n=114 (53.3%) children with ADHD (p-value 0.034). 79 (69.2%) cases diagnosed co-morbid Mental retardation were male and 35 (30.7%) were females.

TABLE NO 1.

SOCIODEMOGRAPHIC FACTORES	FREQUENCY	PERCENT
Mean Age in years	9.50 years (s.d.=2.32)	
Gender of patient		
Male	160	74.8
Female	54	25.2
Schooling of patient		
Attended	103	48.1
Not Attended	111	51.9
Resident of patent		
Rural	105	49.1
Urban	109	50.9
Co-Morbid Mental Retardation		
YES	114	53.3
NO	100	46.7
Age Category		
6 to 8 years	79	36.9
9 to 12years	135	63.1

To predict for any symbolic association, age was transformed categorically (6-8) and (9-12) years (p-value 0.034) (Table 2). Most of the children with co-morbid Mental Retardation were in the age range of 9 to 12 years.

Rural urban breakdown (Figure No 1) of co-morbid Mental Retardation in ADHD children, from urban n=109 ADHD children 62 (56.8%) children had co-morbid Mental Retardation in which 46 are male which is 74.19% and 16 are female which is 25.80%. From rural n=105 ADHD children 52 (49.52%) had co-morbid Mental Retardation in which 33 (63.46%) are male and 19 (36.53%) are female. Co-morbid Mental Retardation when compare urban and rural with gender wise it's significantly present in male gender despite of urban and rural difference (p-value 0.056) (Table no 2).

TABLE 2: Two-way Measures of associations between Mental Retardation and other Predictors.

Age of Children	Co-Morbid Mental Retardation		p-value
	YES	NO	
6 to 8 years	49	30	0.034
9 to 12 years	65	70	
Gender of patient			0.035
Male	79	81	
Female	35	19	
Schooling			0.005
Attended	45	58	
Not Attended	69	42	
Residence			0.173
Rural	52	53	
Urban	62	47	

DISCUSSION

We conducted an institute based study to analyze the prevalence of Mental retardation in ADHD children. Our research findings shows that children with ADHD had higher prevalence of Mental Retardation 53.3% which is statistically significant (p-value 0.035), this is nearly equally to 53.8% Qureshi et al from Aga Khan Hospital Karachi Pakistan [18]. Our study represent the entire urban and rural population of Sindh, but the study by Qureshi et al only represent the class who afford AKU Hospital only and even can't represent the entire Karachi population. The prevalence of Mental Retardation in children with ADHD is equally present in all social classes of the study population. A study from US shows prevalence of Mental Retardation in children with ADHD is 46% which is lower than our finding of prevalence [14]. US study also shows higher rate of co-morbidities in poor versus affluent children and difference is significant 30% vs 8% [14], but our finding were opposite that Mental Retardation is relatively more common in urban population of children (56.8%) then rural population (49.52%). Worldwide studies shows poorer outcome in ADHD children with co-morbid disorders, and had significant social, emotional and psychological problems [16]. Children diagnosed with ADHD had higher ratio of school problems (odds ratio: 5.18) and use frequently health services [14], Children with Mental Retardation respond well to stimulants and educational supports [15], so if diagnose earlier Mental retardation in ADHD children, they respond well to treatment, improve their school problems and lower down their hospital visits.

A study by Syed et al gender ratio was 1:5 male to female [19], which is significantly different from our study findings, whereas Qureshi et al cross section review shows male to female ratio 3:1 [18] which equal to our study finding. In cross section study by Majid et al shows 27% are male and 17.9% are female [20]. Our study finding shows ADHD is more in male and these findings are supported by Majid et al study but in contrast Syed et al study found ADHD more in females [20].

By Peria et al gender difference in co-morbidity of ADHD is 48.3% in male and 51.7% in female [21] it is in contrast to our findings 69.29% in male and 30.7% in female (p-value 0.035). According to previous studies there is no significant difference geographically in ADHD prevalence [11], in contrast our study results shows relatively more ADHD children reported from Urban area n=109 then from rural area n=105 (49.1%). Except from gender difference Mental retardation (mild or serious) is nearly equal in either urban or rural areas as reported by Durkin et al study from Karachi [12]. From urban population 82 (75.22%) were male and 27 (24.77%) were female, mostly male children were reported (P-value 0.17). From Urban children 62 (54.38%) children of ADHD had co-morbid Mental retardation, in which more male 46 (74.19%) then female 16 (25.80%). In the rural population of the study 52 (45.61%) children of ADHD had co-morbid Mental retardation, in which more male 33 (63.46%) then female 19 (36.53%). Co-morbid Mental retardation is more frequent in male despite Urban and rural difference.

CONCLUSION

Prevalence of Co-morbid Mental retardation in children with ADHD is higher. There is an equal ratio of ADHD cases from urban and rural population of the study with or without Co-morbid Mental retardation, in gender breakdown male were commonly present with co-morbid Mental retardation in ADHD children despite their geographic area.

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